

Effect of azolla and inorganic N on rice.^a Coimbatore, India, 1983-84

Treatment ^b	1983 wet season					1983-84 dry season				
	Dry matter production (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)	Dry matter production (t/ha)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Straw yield (t/ha)
Control (no N)	6.4 d	245 d	69 d	2.5 d	4.0 d	6.1 d	212 d	63 d	2.3 d	4.0 d
100 kg N-PU	13.4 b	502 b	91 b	5.9 b	7.7 b	13.1 b	483 b	83 bc	5.5 b	7.6 b
25 kg N-azolla+ 75 kg N-PU	11.0 c	413 c	88 c	5.0 c	6.4 c	10.7 c	397 c	80 c	4.5 c	6.2 c
100 kg N-USG	15.2 a	618 a	100 a	7.0 a	9.0 a	14.8 a	598 a	87 ab	6.5 a	8.4 a
25 kg N-azolla + 75 kg N-USG	15.1 a	565 a	100 a	7.0 a	8.9 a	14.6 a	560 a	89 a	6.4 a	8.4 a

^aMeans followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bN rate = 100 kg/ha.

Effect of cultivation method on the rice crop and the mechanical impediment of Vertisols

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Puddling for transplanted rice facilitates transplanting, maintenance of submergence, and weed control. But in Vertisols, with low infiltration rates, puddling disturbs the soil physical condition and creates problems for field preparation of dry season wheat.

We studied the influence of different cultivation methods on the rice crop and soil mechanical impediment. Treatments — direct drilling (DD), direct transplanting (DT), bullock puddling (BP), and tractor puddling (TP) — were in a randomized block design with four

Table 1. Effect of puddling on penetration force. Jabalpur, India, 1985.

Treatment	Depth (m)	Penetration force (kg/cm ²)	
		Tillering stage	Milk stage
Direct drilling	5	1.49	4.61
	10	4.93	6.26
	15	6.49	7.36
Direct transplanting	5	2.15	4.85
	10	5.30	6.24
	15	6.39	7.49
Bullock puddling	5	1.37	2.74
	10	3.31	6.01
	15	4.37	7.35
Tractor puddling	5	1.02	2.80
	10	4.47	6.18
	15	6.02	7.43

Table 2. Effect of method of cultivation on growth and yield of paddy. Jabalpur, India, 1985.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		Plant height (cm)	Tillers/Plant	Panicle length (cm)
	Grain	Straw			
Direct drilling	4.2	10.6	76.8	6.3	20.8
Direct transplanting	3.3	8.4	75.6	6.4	21.2
Bullock puddling	3.7	9.2	77.8	6.4	21.2
Tractor puddling	3.4	9.4	72.0	6.3	21.3
CD at 0.05	0.7	1.5	ns	ns	no
cv (%)	28	19	—	—	—

replications. Rice variety Ratna was sown 7 Nov 1985. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-40 kg NPK/ha.

Plant height, tiller numbers, panicle length, and grain and straw yields were recorded. Penetration force at tillering and milk stages was measured by penetrometer.

DD gave the highest mechanical impediment (MI), and TP the lowest, irrespective of growth stage (Table 1). The increased magnitude of MI at the

milk stage was attributed to reduced moisture content.

Tillers/ plant, plant height, and panicle length did not differ significantly (Table 2). DD gave the significantly highest grain and straw yield. The differences among DT, BP, and TP were not significant. A similar trend was found with straw yield.

Reduced yield due to puddling is attributed to deterioration of physical conditions of the soil. □

Efficiency of nitrogen fertilizers and a nitrification inhibitor

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We studied the relative efficiency of urea, ammonium sulfate, and potassium nitrate during 1986 kharif (Jun-Sep). Nitrification inhibitor 4-amino-1,2,4-triazole (ATC) was applied at 5% by weight of urea. To restrict NH₃ volatilization, urea-nitrification inhibitor and urea alone treatments were applied

in bands (3 cm below surface) between the rows. N at 110 kg/ha was applied in 3 equal splits: 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting with no standing water.

Soil of the experimental field was Fatehpur loamy sand (Typic Ustipsamment) with pH 8.5, 0.23% organic C, 7 kg Olsen's P/ha and 71 kg ammonium acetate extractable K/ha. Soil percolation rate was about 6 mm/h. Treatments were laid out in a randomized complete block design with four replications. Six-week-old seedlings of rice variety PR106 were transplanted the third week of June. □